

Targeting activated partial thromboplastin time of unfractionated heparin: the role of clinical pharmacist at the cardiac care unit

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Abstract

Background: Unfractionated heparin (UFH) requires precise monitoring, primarily via activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT), to achieve therapeutic anticoagulation and minimize complications. Optimizing UFH therapy demands robust monitoring strategies and collaborative involvement of healthcare professionals, particularly pharmacists.

Objective: This study aimed to evaluate aPTT levels in patients receiving UFH and determine the impact of clinical pharmacists on achieving target aPTT in a cardiac care unit (CCU).

Patients and methods: A prospective observational study was conducted in the CCU of Baghdad Teaching Hospital from February 2023 to January 2024, enrolling patients prescribed UFH.

Results: Of 307 patients, only 21% (n = 65) initially reached therapeutic aPTT levels. Notably, only 1 of 47 patients receiving subcutaneous UFH achieved target aPTT (P = 0.009). Clinical pharmacists performed 80 interventions, resulting in a statistically significant improvement in mean aPTT from 44.1 ± 24.8 to 46.7 ± 24 (P < 0.001). This increased the percentage of patients within the therapeutic range from 21% (n = 65) to 29% (n = 90).

Conclusion: Clinical pharmacist interventions significantly improved aPTT targeting for UFH in the CCU, increasing therapeutic achievement rates despite initially suboptimal levels and highlighting their value in optimizing anticoagulation therapy.

Keywords

activated partial thromboplastin time, cardiac care unit, clinical pharmacy, Iraq, unfractionated heparin

Introduction

Unfractionated heparin (UFH) has been in widespread use since the 1940s for managing deep vein thrombosis, pulmonary embolism, and acute coronary syndromes (Niccolai et al. 2004). When utilized in the appropriate

therapeutic context, UFH proves to be a beneficial and effective treatment; however, its narrow therapeutic range requires careful monitoring (Becattini and Agnelli 2020). If not managed correctly, patients receiving unfractionated heparin could face a heightened risk of

severe bleeding complications, such as intracranial hemorrhage. Furthermore, unfractionated heparin is identified as one of the top five high-alert medications (Biscup-Horn et al. 2008; Kuitunen et al. 2023). The Institute for Safe Medication Practices (ISMP) defines high-alert medications as those that “carry an increased risk of causing significant harm to patients when misused” (Chakraborty et al. 2022).” This risk is reflected in the analysis of errors submitted to MedMARx, a voluntary initiative supported by the United States (US) Pharmacopeia to track medication errors in hospitals across the US. From 1999 to 2002, 2.1% of documented errors in this database were linked to UFH, with 4.5–5.5% resulting in patient harm. The serious consequences tied to this high-alert medication underscore the need for the creation and enforcement of strict protocols regarding its administration (Niccolai et al. 2004; Loria 2012).

Unfractionated heparin (UFH) is a widely used anticoagulant in clinical settings due to its effectiveness in patients with renal impairment, its short half-life, and the availability of a reversal agent. Moreover, it allows for the monitoring of anticoagulation levels using easily accessible laboratory tests. For patients receiving continuous intravenous (IV) UFH, laboratory monitoring is crucial because of the variable pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics that arise from the nonspecific binding of heparin to proteins and endothelial cells, along with patient-specific factors such as weight, age, thrombophilias, liver conditions, lupus anticoagulants, and disseminated intravascular coagulation. Despite its limitations, the activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) remains the most practical and commonly utilized tool for monitoring heparin. The American Heart Association guidelines advise performing an aPTT 6 hours after starting therapy and following every dose adjustment to evaluate the effects of the current dose (McRae et al. 2021). Continuous IV UFH patients are monitored to ensure they achieve and maintain therapeutic aPTT targets.

Key research indicates that delays in reaching therapeutic aPTT anticoagulation and prolonged usage of subtherapeutic anticoagulation correlate with a higher incidence of recurrent venous thromboembolism (VTE) (Becattini and Agnelli 2020). Introducing a clinical pharmacist intervention with a specialized alert for UFH may improve the rate of patients attaining therapeutic aPTT and reduce medication errors (Barry et al. 2021).

Few studies in the literature compare the effects of pharmacists’ interventions on clinical outcomes before and after the intervention, and rare studies have been conducted in low- and middle-income countries, particularly in settings where protocolized UFH use, reagent-specific laboratory calibration, and pharmacist resourcing may vary.

Some examples include antimicrobial stewardship programs and pharmacy clinical interventions focused on cost-saving measures, such as converting intravenous (IV) to oral (PO) medications. Clinical pharmacists are crucial in monitoring aPTT levels during UFH therapy. Their knowledge in pharmacotherapy and patient care ensures

safe and effective administration of UFH, enhancing patient outcomes while reducing the likelihood of complications (Alsulaiman et al. 2016).

Aim of the study

The primary aim of this study was to quantify the proportion of patients achieving a therapeutic aPTT. The secondary aim was to evaluate the impact of predefined clinical pharmacist interventions on achieving and maintaining the target aPTT and to describe the nature of these interventions.

Patients and methods

A single-center, prospective observational study was conducted in the cardiac care unit (CCU) at Baghdad Teaching Hospital, Medical City, from February 2023 to January 2024.

Eligibility criteria

We prospectively enrolled all patients aged ≥ 18 years admitted to the CCU who were initiated on therapeutic-dose unfractionated heparin (UFH) (even if it was 5000 IU subcutaneous every 6 hours according to clinical practice) by the primary cardiology team. The decision to initiate therapy was based on institutional treatment protocols for the following indications:

- Acute coronary syndrome (ACS): Patients with non-ST-elevation ACS (NSTEMI-ACS) or ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI).
- Pulmonary embolism (PE): Patients with confirmed or high clinical suspicion of PE.
- Atrial fibrillation (AF): Patients with high-risk AF requiring bridging therapy.
- Other indications: Conditions requiring therapeutic anticoagulation, such as bridging for mechanical heart valves.

Exclusion criteria

Patients were excluded if they (1) declined to participate; (2) had documented heparin-induced thrombocytopenia (HIT) or severe thrombocytopenia (platelets $< 50,000/\mu\text{L}$); (3) had severe liver disease with baseline coagulopathy; (4) were expected to be on UFH for less than 48 hours; or (5) had incomplete laboratory data.

Study procedure

The data were gathered from patients who had provided consent using a standardized questionnaire and by reviewing their medical records, drug charts, and physician

notes. The data collected included demographic information, preexisting medical conditions, laboratory results, and details of any interventions made by the clinical pharmacist working at the CCU. In the absence of a hospital-specific UFH protocol, the clinical pharmacist ensured UFH optimization by regularly monitoring aPTT and making dose and administration changes guided by the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) guidelines (Konstantinides et al. 2020; Byrne et al. 2023). aPTT monitoring was carried out before and after the interventions, and the results were documented daily.

A 2 mL venous blood sample was collected by a phlebotomy specialist using a 21-gauge needle. The blood was drawn into a sodium citrate (3.2%) tube and sent to the laboratory within one hour. Two samples were collected: the first sample was taken 6 hours after starting unfractionated heparin, administered either intravenously or subcutaneously, and the second was taken 6 hours after changing the unfractionated heparin dose or route of administration.

The standard and therapeutic aPTT ranges were established in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions for the CA-600 coagulation analyzer and the Pathromtin® SL reagent, using the laboratory's locally validated reference interval. The standard range for aPTT was reported to be between 30 and 40 seconds, while the therapeutic range was reported to be between 1.5 and 2.5 times the normal range, according to guideline recommendations (Konstantinides et al. 2020; Byrne et al. 2023).

Data analysis

The patients' data were entered into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. The software generated descriptive statistics for various variables, including demographic characteristics, laboratory investigations, and prescribed medications. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, and the associations between them were tested using Pearson's chi-square test or Fisher's exact test (if 25% or more of the cells had observed or expected values less than 5). In addition, the McNemar test was used for comparison of the same variable on two successive occasions. Continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation, and comparisons of these parameters were assessed using the independent t-test if the dependent variable was dichotomous or analysis of variance (ANOVA) if the dependent variable was multinomial. In addition, the paired t-test was used to compare the same variable mean on two successive occasions. The p-value was considered significant at 0.05 or below. The results were presented in tables, figures, and paragraphs using Microsoft Word version 2016.

Results

The initial number of patients was 467. Based on the inclusion criteria, 307 patients were enrolled, while 169 patients were excluded (Fig. 1).

Descriptive statistics

The average age of the patients was 59.3 ± 13.1 years, with 56.4% male and 43.6% female. The mean BMI was 29.9 ± 6.9 kg/m², and only 21% of the patients were within the normal BMI range. Among the total number of patients, 93 (30.3%) were smokers and 7 (2.3%) were alcohol users. Moreover, 206 patients (67.1%) had hypertension, 175 (57%) had diabetes, 113 (36.8%) had ischemic heart disease (IHD), 70 (22.8%) had heart failure (HF), 58 (18.9%) had atrial fibrillation (AF), 34 (11.1%) had chronic kidney disease (CKD), 21 (6.8%) had cerebrovascular accident (CVA), 14 (4.6%) had cancer, and 44 (14.3%) had other diseases, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Socio-demographic features and comorbidities of the study group (n = 307).

Variables	No.	%
Age groups		
<40 years	25	8.1
40–59 years	129	42.0
60+ years	153	49.8
Mean \pm SD	59.2 \pm 13.1	
Sex		
Male	173	56.4
Female	134	43.6
Body mass index categories		
< 25 kg/m ²	65	21.2
25 - < 30 kg/m ²	115	37.5
\geq 30 kg/m ²	127	41.4
Mean \pm SD	29.9 \pm 6.9	
Social habits		
Smoker	93	30.3
Alcohol	7	2.3
Comorbidities		
Hypertension	206	67.1
Diabetes mellitus	175	57
Ischemic heart disease	113	36.8
Heart failure	70	22.8
Atrial fibrillation	58	18.9
Chronic kidney disease	34	11.1
Cerebrovascular accident	21	6.8
Cancer	14	4.6
Other	44	14.3

Other: valvular heart disease, asthma, COPD, autoimmune diseases, and pregnancy.

The differential diagnosis of the study group

In the study group, most of the patients had been diagnosed with acute coronary syndrome (ACS), comprising 213 patients (69.4% of the total). Their mean aPTT was 42.2 seconds. Fifty-one patients (16.6%) were diagnosed with atrial fibrillation (AF), and their mean aPTT was 44.2 seconds. Thirty-eight patients (12.4%) were diagnosed with pulmonary embolism (PE), with a mean aPTT of 55.2 seconds. A few patients, 5 (1.6%), had been diagnosed with other conditions such as deep vein thrombosis (DVT), left ventricular (LV) thrombus, and bridging therapy, as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 1. Patients enrolled in the study group. HIT: heparin-induced thrombocytopenia; LFT: liver function test.

Activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) level

Based on the aPTT level, the patients were categorized into three groups: therapeutic level, sub-therapeutic level, and supra-therapeutic level. Of the total 307 patients, 228 (74.3%) had sub-therapeutic levels, 65 (21.2%) were at the therapeutic level, and 14 (4.6%) were at the supra-therapeutic level, as shown in Fig. 3.

Intravenous UFH administration versus subcutaneous administration

In this study, on day 1, 260 patients received intravenous (IV) UFH. Of these, 64 (25%) achieved the target aPTT₁

with a mean aPTT of 46 ± 26.3 seconds. However, only 1 patient (2.1%) of the 47 who received subcutaneous UFH reached the target aPTT, with a mean aPTT of 32.8 ± 6.2 seconds. On day 2, 278 patients received IV UFH, and among them, 90 (31%) achieved the target aPTT₂ with a mean aPTT of 47.8 ± 24.7 seconds. None of the 29 patients who received subcutaneous UFH reached the target aPTT, with a mean aPTT of 32.7 ± 3.5 seconds. The difference between the two groups was statistically significant ($P = 0.009$), as shown in Fig. 4.

Clinical pharmacist interventions

The clinical pharmacist made 80 interventions during the study. The majority of interventions (37.5%)

Figure 2. The differential diagnosis of the study group. ACS: acute coronary syndrome; aPTT: activated partial thromboplastin time; AF: atrial fibrillation; PE: pulmonary embolism; DVT: deep vein thrombosis; LV: left ventricular.

involved an increase in the dose of UFH, with a mean of 5991 ± 8339 units. In 31 cases (38.6%), the administration route of UFH was changed from subcutaneous (SC) to intravenous (IV), while in 13 cases (16.3%), the dose of UFH was decreased, with a mean of 5900 ± 5866.7 units. Six cases (7.5%) involved other interventions (e.g., holding heparin), as shown in Fig. 5.

Table 2 shows that the mean aPTT before the interventions was 44.1 ± 24.8 , while after the interventions it was 46.7 ± 24 , with a P-value of less than 0.001.

The percentage of patients within the therapeutic range increased from 21.2% to 29.3%, while the sub-therapeutic range decreased from 74.3% to 64.8%, and the supra-therapeutic range increased from 4.6% to 5.8%. These findings were statistically significant ($P < 0.001$), as shown in Table 3.

Table 2. aPTT levels according to clinical pharmacist intervention.

Level before intervention	aPTT 1		P-value
	Mean (Sec.)	Standard deviation	
Sub-therapeutic	34.2	5.1	<0.001
Therapeutic	59.9	15.1	
Supra-therapeutic	133.1	37.0	
Total	44.1	24.8	
Level after intervention	aPTT 2		P-value
	Mean (Sec.)	Standard deviation	
Sub-therapeutic	33.9	4.8	<0.001
Therapeutic	58.9	10.7	
Supra-therapeutic	119.0	30.4	
Total	46.7	24.0	

aPTT: activated partial thromboplastin time.

Table 3. Changing levels of aPTT range after clinical pharmacist intervention.

Levels of aPTT	aPTT 1		aPTT 2		P-value
	No.	%	No.	%	
Sub-therapeutic	228	74.3%	199	64.8%	< 0.001
Therapeutic	65	21.2%	90	29.3%	
Supra-therapeutic	14	4.6%	18	5.8%	

aPTT: activated partial thromboplastin time.

Figure 3. Distribution of activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) levels among 307 patients.

Figure 4. Relationship between route of administration and activated partial thromboplastin time levels in patients receiving unfractionated heparin. aPTT: activated partial thromboplastin time.

Figure 5. Overview of clinical pharmacist interventions: types and frequency. Others: holding heparin; resend aPTT level.

Discussion

At the cardiac care unit of Baghdad Teaching Hospital, unfractionated heparin (UFH) is used as a primary anticoagulant for various conditions, including acute coronary syndrome, atrial fibrillation, pulmonary embolism, and other thromboembolic disorders. Despite the availability of newer anticoagulants, UFH remains preferred because of its familiarity, accessibility, and guideline-based recommendations.

The current study revealed that a significant number of patients who received UFH failed to attain the desired target aPTT levels. Only 21.2% of the study participants met the target aPTT, compared with 65.7% of patients in Alsulaiman et al. (2016) who achieved the target level. The primary contributing factors leading to this outcome include the use of fixed UFH doses (such as 1000 U/h), interruptions in UFH infusion, subcutaneous heparin administration, heparin resistance, and insufficient monitoring (Smythe et al. 2016; Levy and Connors 2021; Fadheel et al. 2022). These findings emphasize the importance of closely monitoring and carefully administering UFH to ensure optimal patient outcomes during treatment.

To our knowledge and according to the Iraqi Academic Scientific Journals platform (IASJ 2025), this is the first study focusing on monitoring the aPTT of the subcutaneous UFH regimen of 5000 units every 6 hours. This regimen is widely used in some Iraqi hospitals because of the lack of equipment for UFH infusion and the ease of administration (Fadheel et al. 2022). However, this regimen has not been studied or recommended by any guideline. The results of this study provide valuable insights into achieving target aPTT levels in patients receiving UFH via different administration routes. Of the 260 patients who received IV UFH, 64 (25%) attained the target aPTT. In contrast, only 1 patient (2.1%) of the 47 individuals who received subcutaneous UFH achieved the target aPTT.

The findings indicate that administering UFH through intravenous injection is more effective than subcutaneous injection in achieving the desired aPTT levels. The higher percentage of patients who reached their targeted aPTT levels and the relatively longer mean aPTT values in the intravenous UFH group suggest better anticoagulation control, leading to improved therapeutic outcomes. The statistically significant difference in aPTT achievement between the two groups highlights the importance of selecting the appropriate administration route for UFH based on therapeutic goals. These results suggest that subcutaneous UFH may not be as effective as intravenous UFH in achieving optimal anticoagulation because of poor bioavailability (30%) and a slow onset of action of 1 to 2 hours (Hogg and Weitz 2022). This raises concerns about suboptimal treatment effectiveness and an increased risk of thrombotic or bleeding events.

Studies have shown that pharmacists can significantly benefit patients by managing the administration of parenteral and oral anticoagulants. This includes increasing the amount of time patients spend within the therapeutic range, reducing the time spent above it, preventing drug interactions, and decreasing the risk of clinically significant bleeding (Lysogorski et al. 2017).

In the current study, clinical pharmacists made 80 interventions, which included adjusting the dose and changing the route of administration. When a clinical pharmacist intervened, there was a statistically significant improvement in aPTT levels, which increased from 44.1 to 46.7 seconds. [The change in aPTT from 44.1 to 46.7 seconds, while statistically significant, may be limited in clinical relevance and warrants further investigation.] Additionally, the number of patients within the therapeutic range increased from 21% (n = 65) to 29% (n = 90). These results are consistent with previous findings from Lysogorski et al. (2017), which indicated that the selection of an appropriate dosing strategy improved by 9% after pharmacist intervention. However, the difference was not statistically significant because the baseline percentage was already high (84.9% to 96.9%) and due to a small sample size. Another study by Alsulaiman et al. (2016) reported that the mean time to achieve the minimum goal aPTT was 21.8 ± 21.6 hours before pharmacist intervention and 15.4 ± 14.5 hours after intervention ($P = 0.002$). Furthermore, the percentage of patients who achieved the minimum goal aPTT by 24 hours increased from 65.7% before intervention to 82.4% after intervention ($P = 0.004$).

It is essential to recognize that closely monitoring the use of UFH by any healthcare professional may help improve adherence to the protocol. However, the primary responsibility of pharmacists in healthcare systems is to ensure that pharmacotherapy is used correctly. As a result, pharmacists are the most appropriate professionals to oversee the administration of drugs such as heparin, which pose a high risk of error and potential harm.

Conclusion

Only 21% of patients who received unfractionated heparin reached the therapeutic level. Patients who received the subcutaneous (SC) unfractionated heparin regimen remained at sub-therapeutic levels. Clinical pharmacist interventions played a significant role in optimizing the anticoagulation profile.

Limitations of the study

It is important to note that a local protocol for the use of UFH is not available. This resulted in variations in physician, pharmacist, and nursing practices, which could have influenced UFH infusion prescription, dosage adjustment, titration, and monitoring.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalized human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

This study was conducted in full accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. The study protocol was reviewed and formally approved by the Scientific and Ethical Committee of the Iraqi Board for Medical Specializations.

A member of the research team approached each participating patient (or their legally authorized representative if the patient lacked capacity) and provided a detailed verbal explanation of the study. This included its purpose, the nature of the data to be collected from medical records, the voluntary nature of participation, and assurances of data confidentiality.

After having the opportunity to ask questions, patients who agreed to participate had their consent documented by the researcher, including the date and time, in the study-specific data collection form. This procedure was followed for all enrolled participants.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Material preparation, data collection, and analysis were performed by Aymen Zaid Sami, Hasan Ali Farhan, and Hasan Mohammed Abbas. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Aymen Zaid Sami, and all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

The datasets generated or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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